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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“THE FARM OF DREAMS”

He walks the land
Where his life began,
Holding a pail of hope
Beneath the blazing sun.

Muddy feet—where dreams once stuck,
Calloused hands that carve his luck.

He feeds and plants,
And cared the land

Now harvest calls,
The field stands bare,
Yet courage blooms
In open air.

Uncertainty now fade in vanes
For every grains he sowed now bears his name
Success—a dream he once crave
Now reclaimed